

Supplementary Material for

A water-soluble Schiff base ligand and its Al(III) complex: optical properties, computational studies and photocatalytic performance

Hajer Bouznif^{1,2,*}, Licinia L. G. Justino^{2,*}, Telma Costa², Maria I. L. Soares², M. Luísa Ramos², Teresa M. V. D. Pinho e Melo², Nabil Zouari¹ and Rui Fausto^{2,3}

¹ *Laboratory Physico-Chemistry of the Solid State, Department of Chemistry, Faculty of Sciences of Sfax, B. P. 1171, Sfax 3000, University of Sfax, Tunisia*

² *CQC-IMS, Department of Chemistry, University of Coimbra, Rua Larga 3004-535 Coimbra, Portugal*

³ *Spectroscopy@IKU, Faculty of Sciences and Letters, Department of Physics, Istanbul Kultur University, Ataköy Campus, Bakirköy 34156, Istanbul, Turkey*

Corresponding authors e-mails:

bouznifhajer13@gmail.com (Hajer Bouznif) and liciniaj@ci.uc.pt (Licinia L. G. Justino)

Index:

	<u>Page</u>
Figure S1. Experimental and calculated (TD-DFT CAM-B3LYP/6-311++G(d,p)) absorption spectra of MSS and Al(III)/MSS complex (H ₂ O)	2
Figure S2. Diagram of the molecular orbitals involved in the main contributions to the UV-vis absorption spectrum of the I-b-NH conformer of MSS (TD-DFT B3LYP/6-311++G(d,p), IEFPCM (H ₂ O))	2
Figure S3. Diagram of the molecular orbitals involved in the main contributions to the UV-vis absorption spectrum of the III-c-OH conformer of MSS (TD-DFT B3LYP/6-311++G(d,p), IEFPCM (H ₂ O))	3
Figure S4. Diagram of the molecular orbitals involved in the main contributions to the UV-vis absorption spectrum of the Al(III)/MSS complex (TD-DFT B3LYP/6-311++G(d,p), IEFPCM (H ₂ O))	3
Figure S5. Stability of Al(III) / MSS monitored by ¹ H NMR spectroscopy in D ₂ O over 24 h, pH* 4.88; Temp. 298.15 K. *DMSO from synthesis	4
Table S1. Vertical excitation energies (in eV), oscillator strengths (<i>f</i>), wavelengths (<i>λ</i>), and major contributions calculated for MSS (I-b-NH and III-c-OH) and Al(III)/MSS complex (TD-DFT CAM-B3LYP/6-311++G(d,p), IEFPCM (H ₂ O))	4

Figure S1. Experimental and calculated (TD-DFT CAM-B3LYP/6-311++G(d,p)) absorption spectra of MSS and Al(III)/MSS complex (H_2O).

Figure S2. Diagram of the molecular orbitals involved in the main contributions to the UV-vis absorption spectrum of the I-b-NH conformer of MSS (TD-DFT B3LYP/6-311++G(d,p), IEFPCM (H_2O)).

Figure S3. Diagram of the molecular orbitals involved in the main contributions to the UV-vis absorption spectrum of the **III-c-OH** conformer of **MSS** (TD-DFT B3LYP/6-311++G(d,p), IEFPCM (H₂O)).

Figure S4. Diagram of the molecular orbitals involved in the main contributions to the UV-vis absorption spectrum of the **Al(III)/MSS** complex (TD-DFT B3LYP/6-311++G(d,p), IEFPCM (H₂O)).

Figure S5. Stability of **Al(III)/MSS** monitored by ^1H NMR spectroscopy in D_2O over 24 h, $\text{pH}^* 4.88$; Temp. 298.15 K. *DMSO from synthesis.

Table S1. Vertical excitation energies (in eV), oscillator strengths (f), wavelengths (λ), and major contributions calculated for **MSS** (I-b-NH and III-c-OH) and **Al(III)/MSS** complex (TD-DFT CAM-B3LYP/6-311++G(d,p), IEFPCM (H_2O)).

Excited State	Energy (eV)	$\lambda_{\text{calc.}}$ (nm)	$\lambda_{\text{exp.}}$ (nm)	f^a	Major Contributions (%)
MSS (I-b-NH)					
S_1	3.38	367	406	0.36	HOMO-1 \rightarrow LUMO+1 (43%) HOMO \rightarrow LUMO (57%)
S_5	4.65	268	295	0.63	HOMO-3 \rightarrow LUMO+1 (35%) HOMO-2 \rightarrow LUMO (59%)
S_{11}	5.35	232	249	1.18	HOMO-1 \rightarrow LUMO+8 (47%) HOMO \rightarrow LUMO+6 (13%) HOMO \rightarrow LUMO+7 (17%) HOMO \rightarrow LUMO+10 (19%)
MSS (III-c-OH)					
S_1	4.19	296	295	0.19	HOMO-1 \rightarrow LUMO+1 (45%) HOMO \rightarrow LUMO (55%)
S_3	4.92	252	249	0.75	HOMO-3 \rightarrow LUMO+1 (35%) HOMO-2 \rightarrow LUMO (56%)
S_7	5.61	221	-	1.57	HOMO-1 \rightarrow LUMO+4 (21%) HOMO-1 \rightarrow LUMO+7 (27%) HOMO \rightarrow LUMO+5 (30%) HOMO \rightarrow LUMO+6 (18%)
Al (III)/MSS					

S_1	3.65	340	349	0.01	HOMO-1 → LUMO+1 (35%) HOMO → LUMO (65%)
S_2	3.75	331	-	0.14	HOMO → LUMO+1 (40%) HOMO-3 → LUMO+1 (30%)
S_3	4.59	270	277	0.55	HOMO-2 → LUMO (60%) HOMO-3 → LUMO (60%)
S_4	4.76	260	243	0.24	HOMO-2 → LUMO+1 (40%) HOMO-1 → LUMO+6 (15%)
S_{10}	5.46	227	-	0.93	HOMO-1 → LUMO+7 (29%) HOMO → LUMO+3 (14%) HOMO → LUMO+8 (36%) HOMO-1 → LUMO+3 (15%)
S_{12}	5.58	222	-	0.55	HOMO-1 → LUMO+8 (32%) HOMO → LUMO+6 (15%) HOMO → LUMO+7 (31%)

^a Results are shown for the region of energy up to 5.61 eV and calculated oscillator strength > 0.01